

This, I believe, is the spirit in which the framers of our constitution wrote chapter 5 which states:

Chapter 5:

12. 2. Every person in Ghana, whatever his race, place of origin, political opinion, colour, religion, creed or gender shall be entitled to the fundamental human rights and freedoms of the individual contained in this Chapter but subject to respect for the rights and freedoms of others and for the public interest.

15.1 The dignity of all persons shall be inviolable (Respect for Human Dignity)

17.1. All persons shall be equal before the law. (Equality & Freedom from Discrimination)

17.2. A person shall not be discriminated against on grounds of gender, race, colour,

ethnic origin, religion, creed or social or economic status.

They saw it fit to explicitly protect a number of human attributes and traits that had previously been used by many other groups in times past to either discriminate or in some way target other humans for harm, violating their human rights. These traits are: **gender, race, colour, ethnic origin, religion, creed or social or economic status**

Sexuality, like each of these traits, is a human trait. And so it is my belief that even though it may not have been written directly into the constitution, it meets the criteria for protection set out by our constitution.

This bill is a perfect example of why sexuality should be explicitly protected by our constitution. It arranges for prosecution and social discrimination a number of people identified solely by their sexual orientation. It even goes so far as to explicitly criminalise individuals for their gender assignment (transgender), a direct contradiction to one of the traits outlined by the constitution for protection: gender.

Conclusion:

Given all the above points, I strongly urge this proposed bill be rejected as it does not accord with Ghana's democratic values of freedom and justice for all its citizens.